

Successful Treatment with CAR- T Cells in a Patient with Immune Thrombocytopenia Associated with Castleman Disease

Xiaotian Zhang¹, Hai Cheng^{1,#}

¹Department of Hematology, Affiliated Hospital of Xuzhou Medical University, Xuzhou 221002, China

Abstract: Multicentric Castleman disease (MCD), a rare lymphoproliferative disorder of incompletely understood etiology, is manifested as enlarged multiple lymph node and multiple organs involvement. The best therapeutic option for this disease remains unknown. A 21-year-old male patient of MCD with swelling lymph nodes received combination chemotherapy treatment with unsatisfactory efficacy. He developed thrombocytopenia during disease progression and failed steroid treatment. His platelet increased to normal level on day 27 of receiving infusion of humanised anti-CD19 chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) T cells (1×10^6 cells/kg) and murine anti-BCMA CAR T cells (0.6×10^6 cells/kg). He has a stable platelet count and no evidence of progression of lymphadenopathy for 45 months at this writing. This case report reminds clinicians to be aware of the potential clinical value of CAR T cells therapy in MCD.

Keywords: Chimeric antigen receptor T cells; Castleman disease; Immune thrombocytopenia.

Introduction

Castleman disease (CD) is a rare lymphoproliferative disorder that was first defined by Castleman in 1956^[1]. The disease has been classified into unicentric CD(UCD) or multicentric CD(MCD) according to the clinical features and into hyalin-vascular type, plasma cell type or mixed type according to the histological findings^[2,3]. MCD is known to be associated with autoimmune phenomena, including immune thrombocytopenia (ITP)^[4]. A wide variety of therapeutic approaches have been attempted^[5]. However, the best therapeutic option for ITP accompanied by MCD is not clearly defined. Here we report on a patient with ITP associated with MCD successfully treated with chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) T cells.

Case presentation

In August 2010, a 21-year-old male presented with a 4-month history of multiple swelling lymph nodes at a county-level public hospital. A cervical lymph node biopsy was suggestive of Castleman disease (CD) and he was referred to our hospital for further care. Her pathology review documented plasma-cell CD (Fig. 1). His peripheral blood counts revealed a white blood cell count (WBC) of $7.83 \times 10^9/L$, a hemoglobin (Hb) of 80 g/L and a platelet (PLT) of $401 \times 10^9/L$. Liver function revealed elevated serum total protein of 115.9 g/L and globulin of 95 g/L, low serum albu-

min of 37.4 g/L. Renal function was normal. Serum IgG increased to 30.5 g/L. Urine light chain λ and light chain κ respectively increased to 171 mg/L and 409 mg/L. HBsAg, HBeAg and HBeAb were positive and HIV antibody was negative. Bone marrow examination revealed no dysplasia. Abdominal ultrasound revealed a splenomegaly ($13.5 \text{ cm} \times 4.3 \text{ cm}$) and chest computed tomography revealed swelling of mediastinal lymph nodes and bilateral axillary lymph nodes. He was diagnosed with plasma-cell Multicentric CD (MCD)^[6] and treated with combination chemotherapy (fludarabine (three daily doses of 30 mg/m^2) and cyclophosphamide (three daily doses of 250 mg/m^2)[FC], as 1 cycle) \times 2 cycles. After that, he was not regularly admitted to our hospital for follow-up visit because of no discomfort symptoms. In April 2013, the patient was treated with a course of combination chemotherapy (etoposide, cyclophosphamide, epirubicin, vincristine, prednisone[E-CHOP]) again because of progressive swelling of bilateral axillary lymph nodes, whose lymph node biopsy demonstrated CD, which improved the condition.

In July 2017, he suddenly developed multiple petechiae and ecchymosis on the skin and mucous membrane of the whole body. Thrombocytopenia with $\text{PLT } 2 \times 10^9/L$ was observed. A bone marrow examination revealed no evidence of tumor or infection in the marrow and thrombocytogenic megakaryocyte of 2.7%. Liver, renal, thyroid function were normal. Autoimmune antibodies were negative. Viral infections, including HBV, HCV, HEV, HIV, TP, were excluded. Ultrasound examination revealed swelling of multiple lymph nodes including bilateral neck, armpit and groin areas, the largest volume of which was about $4.3 \text{ cm} \times 1.6 \text{ cm}$. The spleen is normal in size. The patient was diagnosed with immune thrombocytopenia (ITP) associated with MCD.

He was started on prednisone at the dose of $1 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{d}^{-1}$ with no increasing trend of platelets for 10 days of treatment. Then the patient was treated with combined regimen of prednisone and recombinant human thrombopoietin (rhTPO) with a dose of 300

Correspondence: Cheng Hai. E-mail: hai_cheng@vip.sina.com. Department of Hematology, Affiliated Hospital of Xuzhou Medical University, 99 West Huaihai Round, Xuzhou 221002, China.

Received 13 November 2021; Revised 20 January 2022; Accepted 7 March 2022; Available Online 20 April 2022

DOI: [10.54457/DR.202201003](https://doi.org/10.54457/DR.202201003)

© The Author(s) 2022. This is an open access article under the CC BY 4.0 license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fig. 1. Hematoxylin and eosin staining of a cervical lymph node at diagnosis.

A. Images of sections from the patient's lymph node biopsy. There was a tight concentric layering of lymphocytes at the follicular periphery resulting in an onion-skin appearance.

B. The lymph node lesion demonstrated sheet-like proliferation of plasma cells in the interfollicular area. The CD20, CD79a, CD3, CD45Ro, CD38, CD138, CD23, CD21, Ki-67, bcl-2, λ, κ expression was positive by immunohistochemistry check.

IU/kg/d. PLT increased to $55 \times 10^9/L$ at day 6. rhTPO was discontinued as result of PLT $99 \times 10^9/L$ at day 11 and the patient insisted on discharge. PLT decreased to $4 \times 10^9/L$ during the reduction of 25% prednisone and the treatment regimens were adjusted to methylprednisolone ($0.8 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{d}^{-1}$). PLT showed a brief upward trend and decreased again to $24 \times 10^9/L$. Due to the failure of corticosteroid therapy, the patient consented to CAR T cells therapy through discussion. CD19 and BCMA expression of previous axillary lymph node biopsy was positive by immunohistochemistry check. Fludarabine (three daily doses of $30 \text{ mg}/\text{m}^2$) and cyclophosphamide (one daily doses of $750 \text{ mg}/\text{m}^2$) were used to deplete lymphocytes before infusion of humanised anti-CD19 CAR T cells (1×10^6 cells/kg) and murine anti-BCMA CAR T cells (0.6×10^6 cells/kg). 10 days after CAR T cells infusion, the PLT increased to $60 \times 10^9/L$ (Fig. 2). Repeat hematologic evaluation at 24 days showed PLT $127 \times 10^9/L$ without cytokine release syndrome during the period. On day 43, ultrasonography showed multiple lymph nodes shrank compared to before, the largest volume of which was about $3.4 \text{ cm} \times 1.2 \text{ cm}$. The patient had a stable platelet count and no evidence of progression of lymphadenopathy for 45 months after CAR T cell therapy.

Fig. 2. The changes of platelet after CAR-T cells therapy.

Discussion

MCD is rarely asymptomatic and frequently require systemic

therapy. Some patients present with autoimmune pancytopenia, hypoalbuminemia, hypergammaglobulinemia, polylymphadenopathy and elevated ESR. Surgical excision alone is rarely curative and most patients usually require systemic therapy. Many therapies have been used for MCD, including combination anti-IL-6 antibody, anti-CD-20 antibody, steroids, chemotherapy, immunomodulator and in intractable cases even autologous stem cell transplantation^[5,7]. However, some patients still experience relapse. In the early stage of the disease, our patient received 2 courses of FC and 1 courses of E-CHOP regimen treatment with unsatisfactory efficacy. He developed thrombocytopenia during disease progression. Therapy with steroid is the first-line treatment for ITP^[8] and one of the effective treatment options for MCD. However, our patient failed steroid treatment. In recent years, CAR T cells has been more and more applied in the treatment of relapsed and refractory hematologic malignancies and has achieved encouraging efficacy^[9-11]. Some literature has indicated therapeutic potential of chimeric antigen receptor therapies in autoimmune diseases^[12-14]. It is well known that the prominent pathological feature plasma-cell type MCD is the proliferation of plasma cells, part of which express CD19 and BCMA^[15,16], in the follicular area. The immunohistochemistry check showed that CD19 and BCMA expression of previous axillary lymph node biopsy was positive in our patient. This is why we chose CD19 and BCMA as targets for CART therapy. The platelet increased to normal level without relapse and no evidence of progression of lymphadenopathy for 45 months, suggesting that the CAR T cells played an important role.

In conclusion, this is the first report of patient with ITP associated with MCD treated with CAR T cells, suggesting that CAR T cells therapy may be extended to this patient population as one of the treatment options available.

Significance Statement

Many therapies have been used for MCD. However, some patients still experience relapse. In recent years, CAR T cells has been more and more applied in the treatment of relapsed and refractory hematologic malignancies and has achieved encouraging efficacy. To our knowledge, this is the first report of patient with ITP associated with MCD treated with CAR T cells. This case re-

port reminds clinicians to be aware of the potential clinical value of CAR T cells therapy in MCD.

Abbreviations

BCMA, B-cell maturation antigen; CAR, chimeric antigen receptor; CD, Castleman disease; CD19, cluster of differentiation 19; E-CHOP, etoposide, cyclophosphamide, epirubicin, vincristine, prednisone; FC, Fludarabine, Cyclophosphamide; Hb, hemoglobin; HBV, Hepatitis B Virus; HCV, Hepatitis C Virus; HEV, Hepatitis E Virus; HIV, Hepatitis I Virus; IL-6, interleukin-6; ITP, immune thrombocytopenia; MCD, Multicentric Castleman disease; PLT, platelet; rhTPO, recombinant human thrombopoietin; TP, *Treponema pallidum*; UCD, unicentric CD; WBC, white blood cell count.

Funding

This research was supported by Young Medical Talents Foundation of Jiangsu Province (QNRC2016793).

Conflicts of interest

All authors declared that there are no conflicts of interest.

Authors' contributions

XTZ wrote the manuscript, analyzed all data. HC reviewed the manuscript.

References

- [1] Castleman B, Iverson L, Menendez VP. Localized mediastinal lymphnode hyperplasia resembling thymoma. *Cancer* 1956, 9: 822-830.
- [2] Peterson BA, Frizzera G. Multicentric Castleman's disease. *Semin Oncol* 1993, 20: 636-647.
- [3] Herrada J, Cabanillas F, Rice L, et al. The clinical behavior of localized and multicentric Castleman disease. *Ann Intern Med* 1998, 128: 657-662.
- [4] Kojima M, Nakamura N, Tsukamoto N, et al. Clinical implications of idiopathic multicentric Castleman disease among Japanese: a report of 28 cases. *Int J Surg Pathol*, 2008, 128: 657-662.
- [5] Van Rhee F, Voorhees P, Dispenzieri A, et al. International, evidence-based consensus treatment guidelines for idiopathic multicentric Castleman disease. *Blood*, 2018, 132(20): 2115-2124.
- [6] Fajgenbaum DC, Uldrick TS, Bagg A, et al. International, evidence-based consensus diagnostic criteria for HHV-8-negative/idiopathic multicentric Castleman disease. *Blood*, 2017, 129(12): 1646-1657.
- [7] Roca B. Castleman's Disease. A Review. *AIDS Rev*. 2009, 11(1): 3-7.
- [8] Neunert C, Terrell DR, Arnold DM, et al. American Society of Hematology 2019 guidelines for immune thrombocytopenia. *Blood Adv*, 2019, 3(23): 3829-3866.
- [9] Pan J, Yang JF, Deng BP, et al. High efficacy and safety of low-dose CD19-directed CAR-T cell therapy in 51 refractory or relapsed B acute lymphoblastic leukemia patients. *Leukemia*, 2017, 31(12): 2587-2593.
- [10] Yan Z, Cao J, Cheng H, et al. A combination of humanised anti-CD19 and anti-BCMA CAR T cells in patients with relapsed or refractory multiple myeloma: a single-arm, phase 2 trial. *Lancet Haematol*, 2019, 6(10): e521-e529.
- [11] Ramos CA, Grover NS, Beaven AW, et al. Anti-CD30 CAR-T Cell Therapy in Relapsed and Refractory Hodgkin Lymphoma. *J Clin Oncol*, 2020, 38(32): 3794-3804.
- [12] Ellebrecht CT, Bhoj VG, Nace A, et al. Reengineering chimeric antigen receptor T cells for targeted therapy of autoimmune disease. *Science*, 2016, 353(6295): 179-184.
- [13] Su M, Zhao C, Luo, S. Therapeutic potential of chimeric antigen receptor based therapies in autoimmune diseases. *Autoimmun Rev*, 2021: 102931.
- [14] Yeison SZ, Gloria V. Are chimeric antigen receptor T cells (CAR-T cells) the future in immunotherapy for autoimmune diseases? *Inflamm Res*, 2021, 70(6): 651-663.
- [15] Carpenter RO, Evbuomwan MO, Pittaluga S, et al. B-cell maturation antigen is a promising target for adoptive T-cell therapy of multiple myeloma. *Clin Cancer Res*, 2013, 19: 2048-2060.
- [16] Li XC, Ding Y, Zi MT, et al. from bench to bedside. *Immunol Lett*, 2017, 183: 86-95.